

Sociological Impact of Globalization on dietary patterns and Health in Pakistan

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Abstract

Fast food and other global food consumption are quickly increasing day by day. People's increased consumption of fast food and global food generates a slew of behavioral and health difficulties. People have become increasingly disconnected from traditional and hygienic foods as a result of fast food. Globalized food may boost market value, but it is also a major contributor to the poor health of middle-aged and young people. The primary goal of this term paper is to learn how globalization influences people's dietary choices and how this influences their health. The data is collected through a long literature review and then the relevant data is utilized for this paper. As a phenomenon, globalization is currently used in every structural, cultural, and traditional shift, including business, education, cuisine, and the economy. People eat globalized or fast food to glamorize their lifestyles or meals for modernism, as we all know because humans are drawn to all that is beautiful and exciting. Stop junk food marketing because it is harmful to people's health.

Keywords: globalization, food, health

1. Introduction

Global food systems are being significantly impacted by globalization. Food diversity and availability are increasing as a result of changing food systems, yet not everyone has access to this food. These advancements are connected in numerous ways. market liberalization, market urbanization, increased wealth, and foreign direct investment. Competition for a market share of food purchases tends to intensify as strong new players enter the system, like massive international fast food and retail chains. The losers are small neighborhood organizations, traditional food markets, and, to a lesser extent, vendors selling "street dinners" and other food products. Even though almost all nations look to be moving in a similar direction, different regions and nations are changing their food systems at different rates and depths. Examples from particular nations can be useful in identifying factors that could affect the rate at which these changes take place and how they affect the population's nutritional status.

Adamczyk, (2005) Globalization affects each and everything in the world we discuss how globalization affects food behavior and how the changes in behavior affect food in Pakistan Every society's dietary habits are unique, and ours is a highly traditional one. Pakistan has three distinct cuisine or dietary patterns: a fat and sweet pattern, a fruit and vegetable pattern, and a seafood and yogurt style. This is Pakistan's predominant eating pattern, although as a result of globalization, food patterns are changing, with fast food becoming the norm. As a result, Pakistanis are suffering from a variety of health problems. Three categories can be used to analyze how globalization has affected consumer food behavior: it's market environment & conditions, the methods by which consumers satisfy their requirements, and the ordering and structure of these demands. The rise of hypermarkets, quick-service restaurant chains, retail infrastructure, and regulatory regulations governing consumer protection are all factors that pertain to the initial element of worldwide food consumption.

The second category is linked to changing purchasing and eating habits, as well as new brands and assortments in certain customer categories. Consumer habits and preferences are unified due to economic, social, and technological changes spread across the globe by globalization. Buckley et al. (2007) observe that globalization and the ferritization of consumption are causing more consumers to seek comfort and time-saving solutions. Changes in agriculture and food systems are described by Erickson (2008). Agrochemicals, hybrid plants, and, more recently, genetically engineered plants are among them. Changes to food production are designed to achieve high performance, size, and shape that is especially well-suited to brand-name items, as well as improvements to distribution and marketing systems that aid in order. Food is becoming more and more internationalized. The expansion of fast-food restaurants in the nation is mostly due to globalization.

Popkin, (1993) In 1970, there were 30000 fast food restaurants in the United States; today, there are 233000. This study demonstrated how fast food is growing and evolving day by day. The foundation of dietary patterns, which have been connected to the accelerated spread of adiposity and the way of eating chronic illnesses globally, is the process of globalization. The nature of the food supply chain is altered by globalization, which has an impact on the availability, variety, cost, and desirability of foods.

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The mass culture is a dynamic, revolutionary force that blurs the culture setup and eliminates class, custom, and taste divisions, implying that it has a substantial impact on the development of consumer behavior, lifestyles, and preferences. Regmi et al., (2001) As a result of this rapid growth in the fast-food industry, health problems are surfacing daily and in increasingly severe forms. That there is growing concern around the world about the alarming trend of fast-food consumption and its associated cardiometabolic effects, such as overweight and obesity. The goal of this study was to look at the current evidence on the negative impact of a fast-food diet on cardiometabolic risk variables. Since the beginning of globalization, food imports such as cereals and cereal goods, cashew nuts, and edible oils have increased. Many food imports have been liberalized by placing them on "open general license," which does not require government approval. On several food goods, import tariffs have been decreased to nil or zero. As people's incomes rise, their eating options expand. Consumption of cereals declines, whereas consumption of other meals rises. Even though people spend a lot of money. Although they spend a lesser proportion of their income on food, they spend more in absolute terms. The most diverse food basket is found in cities.

People in cities eat fewer bowls of cereal and more other foods. In the city, protective foods including legumes, fruits and vegetables, milk, eggs, and meat (particularly mutton) are readily available. We looked at the consumption basket at the state level in addition to the change in consumption patterns over time at the national level. What you eat, how you consume it, and how it represents to you are all parts of your culinary culture. Some culinary traditions have gained popularity on a global scale. Many English speakers will request a cappuccino rather than a milky coffee due to the prominence of Italian coffee culture. Along with consumer behavior changes, the cultural and social environment wherein policies are applied has an impact on dietary results. In addition to allowing for the "Coca-Colonization" of consumer habits, the dynamic, competitive dynamics unleashed by globalization also enable niche market product adaption.

Narbro et al., (1999) This is important for public awareness that fast food affects our health in various ways, including the brain, central nervous system, reproductive system, and respiratory system. Fast food may temporarily satiate your appetite, but the long-term effects are dangerous and undesirable. Fast food and baked goods eaters are 51 percentage points more likely to experience depression than non-consumers. Your fertility may be impacted by fast food ingredients. One study found phthalates in all kinds of ready meals, especially pizza and burgers. Phthalates are chemicals that may interfere with or impair your body's reproductive hormones. Exposure to these drugs at high doses may have negative effects on reproduction, including abnormal births.

French et al., (2001) Traditional meals and dishes have such a rich history in staple food, regional cuisine, or local cuisine and are by definition traditional. Globalization has brought about changes in food systems, which have created both challenges and opportunities. Fewer people stand between both the farmer and the buyer in local food systems as opposed to commercial food systems since they function with much less food supply chain and more direct marketing. Face-to-face interactions subsequently forge connections within local food systems, possibly resulting in higher social intimacy and trust among producers and consumers. Other factors that affect food choices include biological ones like hunger, appetite, and taste, as well as economic ones like price, availability, and cost, as well as physical ones like access, education, skills (like cooking), and time.

This research aimed to establish a link between fast food and developments in globalization and urbanization. Globalization, according to this study, is a driving force behind changes in cultural norms, especially consumer fast food consumption. It also explained the variables (globalization) and their effects (Food behavior). It is encouraging to see that conventional food habits still play an important role in rural populations' contemporaneous food habits despite trends toward nutrition transition in the Uttarakhand hills. As a result, the potential outcome of trying to reverse trends in favor of dietary expansion rather than nutritional reduction holds promise.

As a society, we are dealing with serious health issues.

- In terms of lifespan among developed nations, the United States comes in at number 10.
- Because of ongoing health problems like depression, our workforce is plagued with absenteeism and poor productivity.
- Chronic disease treatment accounts for 78 percent of healthcare spending.

Nowadays, a lot of scientists think that diet plays a part in these problems. Today, experts believe that a system of cellular dysfunction is to blame for the development of ailments including type two diabetes, overweight, cardiovascular disease, stroke, and some types of cancer. Previously, they believed that a singular mutated gene was to blame for conditions like these. And a portion of this dysfunction can be attributed to the food we eat.

2. Methodology

This conceptual article is arranged by doing extensive research from the literature. Different research articles and books are analyzed. Initially, article titles were analyzed, and then relevant materials are selected. Different videos and websites are also watched and the relevant data are entered in this conceptual paper.

3. Discussion

Fast food and other sorts of globalized meals are consumed by a significant number of individuals. Fast food is the most popular type of food consumed by people. In Pakistan, fast food restaurants such as McDonald's, KFC Fri-chicks, Pizza Hut, Burger King, Hardees, and a variety of others operate. Fast food has positive and negative features, but most of the negative aspects manifest as health problems. There is a lot of debate over fast food and its impact on people's health in today's culture. Fast food is consumed for the enjoyment of it. Alternatively, some individuals consume it to glamorize their daily meals, and the most essential thing is that fast food is accessible at low prices in the market and does not require much time to prepare. As a result, employed individuals favor fast food or any other type of globalized food over their indigenous foods. Global food and dietary pattern affect the human body, culture, and economic status in many ways. In Pakistan, especially diet habits are changing day by day. In rural areas, the diet patterns are the same as before but in urban areas, because everything is changing with globalization so it has a great effect on food also, and due to this many serious problems are rising at a rapid rate. Everyone is in a rush these days, and there is no time to cook at home, and traditional foods take a long time to prepare, therefore that is the main reason. Every fast-food outlet has a drive-through window so that customers may get their meals quickly. People find this method to be simple, which is why it is rapidly gaining traction in our culture. The McDonaldization theory states that all of the tactics and phases in the fast-food chain are how it became a global trend through globalization. The primary concept of McDonaldization is built on three factors: predictability, standardization, and accessibility. Obesity, hyperactivity, sadness, and anxiety are all problems that fast food causes in children. Obesity causes chronic issues such as heart attacks and other heart problems, type 2 diabetes, cancer, high blood pressure, and so on.

There are some positive and negative aspects of fast food on the lives and health of people who consume a lot of fast or globalized food. The positive aspects are that they save time, are easy to purchase, and online ordering makes it even easier to get this type of food in 30 minutes with just one call. However, there are fewer positives and numerous negatives. When we eat fast food or globalized food, our bodies experience a variety of side effects because it is high in oils and sugar and low in healthy ingredients like proteins, fibers, calcium, iodine, and so on. When our bodies don't get enough of these nutrients, our organs begin to dysfunctional. The following are some of the effects:

3.1. Atopy

Eating fast food three times a week has been associated with a variety of atopic illnesses such as asthma and rhinitis. Asthma rates are about 40% higher in teenagers and over 25% higher in younger children. If children consume fast food more than three times a week, their mathematics and other learning skills would deteriorate.

Overconsumption of calories, fats, sweets, and carbohydrates is known as constipation. This is the most common cause of constipation in people of all ages.

3.2. Depression

Obesity can impair a child's self-esteem compared to a child who does not consume fast food, which can lead to depression. Even if they are not obese, some youngsters who eat junk food have a higher risk of depression. Depression

has an impact on a child's growth and development, as well as their academic achievement and social interactions. It also raises the likelihood of children committing suicide.

3.3. Sleep Disorder

Caffeine in soda drinks can create bedtime disturbances, resulting in sleep disturbances in persons.

3.4. Hyperactivity

Another problem created by this cuisine is hyperactivity, which is very dangerous for everyone and is noticed in those who eat a lot of food from outside.

3.5. Reproductive System Effect

Fast eating and fast-food additives affect your reproduction. Phthalates are found in fast food. Phthalates are substances that can interfere with the body's reproductive hormones. It has the potential to cause reproductive problems in both men and women, including birth abnormalities and infertility.

4. Major Outcomes

The major outcomes of the study are that globalization changes everything in the world whether it is social cultural or economic things. So same is the case with food patterns. In Pakistan, many of the food habits are changed just because of globalization advancement in everything due to urbanization and migration life becomes more hectic to not spend a lot of time in the kitchen and making food they are shifted to fast food or other foods which are available at very cheap rates in restaurants. Due to these dietary habits, people are physically becoming unhealthy many problems are arising day by day. Chronic diseases are increasing at a rapid rate. Many children are suffering from malnutrition and dysfunctions of the organs just because their parents are supposed to take food from outside.

In rural areas, people are as fit and healthy as before because they are in contact with nature and the natural products of dairy rather than dairy. The children are more intellectual and physically strong as compared to the children who have their food patterns changed by the global food. Global food does not only include fast food every food which is not from our culture like Italian, Chinese, Thai, and many other forms of food included in global food can cause serious issues to health and also disturb the culture and economy of the family or the society.

5. Conclusion

This study suggests that globalization has significantly impacted our eating habits and that these habits affect our health in several ways. It has an impact on our nervous system, reproductive system, and a variety of other body organs. There are some favorable effects on the body and many more harmful effects. We also know from this study that globalization, food, and health are all linked.

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